

2017 Dell's Sustainability Report Analysis

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Abstract:

Sustainability report is one of the important documents being issued by the companies either due to the pressure by the stakeholders, or due to the importance of meeting the Sustainable Development Goals or any other different reasons. I have studied the corporate social responsibility report of Dell Technology Inc. in order to understand how the company is applying and meeting its goals, at the same time; I have analyzed the report and criticized the weaknesses on the report.

Note:

Your comments and suggestions are more than welcome as I accept critics because they help me to improve myself.

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Introduction

Corporate social responsibility is a type of social accounting. Social accounting is basically the practices and the activities of an organization to solve some social problems such as employment conditions, sexual equality, health & safety and many other issues. (Rob, 1997).

Organizations are communicating their social activities to their stakeholders by releasing a report named “corporate social responsibility”. This report is being issued at least annually, but in general; based on the policy of the company. In this research, I chose Dell Technologies to analyze and criticize the CSR report for 2017-year end by answer the following questions:

- 1) What are CSR goals are aligned with SDGs? and
- 2) What information the report is missing?

Dell Technologies is one of the leading global end-to-end technology providers. It operates in IT software, hardware and provides IT services solutions with its traditional infrastructure and emerging multi-cloud technologies which enable the customers to build their own digital future (Form 10-K, 2019). Before I go into more details, I have to highlight that in this study, I have covered 2017-year end, so whatever information or analysis have been done here should be referred to 2017-year end and before.

The company had a headcount of approximately 138,000 employees till the end of 2017 (marcotrends.net, 2019). Its wide range of products and the services provided made the company a leading one in the technology industry. Dell is producing its products to have effects on: (Dell Technologies, 2018)

a) Economy

Dell’s products are being highly used by big firms, organizations, NGOs and many other types of customers in order to help their business to develop and become wider. With having a such wide range of products, the company has a huge number of employees which can help the company to meet the markets’ requirements and stay in the markets as a leading company.

b) Environment

One of the examples is that the company runs its technology in drones which are being used by the farmers. These drones can monitor the trees and discover the diseases earlier than usual, so the farmers take actions before other trees get infected. However, since we are talking about the environment, we should mention that Dell is the largest recycler of e-waste in the world with services in 83 countries.

c) People

One of the examples is that Dell sells its products to many different schools and universities to help them in the learning process in addition to volunteerism toward helping communities overcome challenges and thrive such as the activities in Argentina.

Dell's CSR report

Dell is releasing corporate social responsibility (thereafter, “CSR”) report as a way of communication between the management and the stakeholders. When we talk about stakeholders, we have to highlight the fact that Freeman defined the stakeholders as the groups who are getting affected by the organizations’ activities (Freeman, 2004). This wide definition can lead us to understand that stakeholders can be any party being affected by the corporation’s activities. If we apply this definition on my case study, I would say that the stakeholders in my case are any customer, supplier, shareholder, employee and even the environment as it is being affected by the operations of the company. This is why Dell issues its CSR report, almost; in a yearly basis. However, according to the CSR report which was issued by the company in 2018 for the year end 2017, the company is adopting Global Reporting Initiative (thereafter; “GRI”) standards when issuing the report of the CSR (Dell Technologies, 2018). For the readers who don’t know what GRI standards are, GRI standards, basically; are standards being implemented and issued by the GRI Framework which is an international independent standards organization specialized in issuing standards for the CSR reports to help users to understand and communicate their impact on the society and environment such as climate change, human rights, etc. These standards explain what the company has to report, in other words; they provide guidance on what information the company has to disclose in its CSR report.

I have compared the goals and the vision of the company which have been disclosed in the CSR report and I noticed that some of them meet the Sustainable Development Goals (thereafter “SDGs”). Before we go into details, SDGs are social and environmental goals were implemented by the United Nation to be met by 2030. The below picture shows these goals for a better understanding (aer.eu, 2019).

Dell's SDGs

Since the SDGs are somehow international goals for many companies and organizations including non-profit organizations, I have to speak about Dell's SDGs. In other words, I have to compare what Dell disclosed in its report in compliance with the SDGs, and later on, I will check the accuracy and completeness of these disclosures as disclosures without being checked and traced to other resources wouldn't be enough, therefore; in "*is the information real?*" section I will compare the SDGs according to Dell's report with other resources to ensure the accuracy but before I do that, let us have a look at what SDGs Dell is adopting. (Dell Technologies, 2018):

a) No poverty

The company provides online learning opportunities and programs for poor children to enhance their knowledge and experience so they can get income in the future. For example, for the people who live in rural areas or suburban migrant communities, when rural and migrant students fall behind in a subject, they cannot get extra help from their teachers, who are not permitted to tutor after school, and they cannot get help from their parents.

b) Health

The company is trying its best to be environmentally responsible as Dell engages the employees in a number of environmental, health and safety activities. These activities include maintaining high waste diversion and recycling rates, hosting environmental fairs, health and wellness education, tree planting, and park clean-up events.

c) Education

As a global technology provider and corporate citizen, Dell sees itself firsthand in giving access to quality education and technology which can help people in reaching their full potential. It applies its technology, expertise, funding and volunteerism toward helping communities overcome challenges and thrive by doing the following:

- 1) Innovating new technologies for Brazilian students' solar-powered boats
- 2) Promoting new generations of readers in Argentina
- 3) Shrinking the rural-urban educational divide in China
- 4) Empowering Israeli youth to build brighter future
- 5) Advancing the diagnosis and treatment of pediatric cancer

d) Gender equality

Lesbian, gay, bisexual and transgender (LGBT) people face legal and cultural challenges in many regions of the world, but at Dell, the employees and the management share one global culture of acceptance. One of their outlets for fostering this culture is Pride, their employee resource group (ERG) for LGBT team members and their allies.

e) Sustainable clean water

The company is applying its technology and try to study how to improve the efficiency of water use.

f) *Clean energy*

Dell focuses on energy conservation, renewable energy use and waste reduction. Use technology for renewable energy.

g) *Climate change*

Dell sees itself as environmental responsible as it is trying to create an eco-friendly product or initiative. It's about incorporating sustainability into everything they do, while using their technology and expertise to innovate on behalf of their customers, their communities and the planet.

h) *Life below water*

Dell takes care about the problem of the plastic in the sea. Many sea creatures are eating these microplastics that look like phytoplankton, the small marine plants that serve as their food source. Because phytoplankton are the "first course" on the ocean's food chain, the ingested plastics can potentially affect every level of the chain, all the way up to humans. Dell has program to collect plastic from waterways, beaches, rivers and coastal areas. Collecting from such areas is key to preventing pollution.

Measurements

Dell is measuring its performance based on three different criteria which will be explained in this section (Dell Technologies, 2018).

a) *2020 legacy of good plan*

It is an internal plan with the idea that technology should be a driver of human progress. The company believes that it can unlock health, happiness and prosperity by helping all people reach their full potential and share in the common good.

b) *Self-assessment performance against GRI*

The company compares its CSR report to the international standards (GRI standards).

c) *The GRI index*

Similar to the second point, but this should be done by third party. It is basically a checklist being done by the GRI framework in order to compare the CSR reporting of a company with the standards the framework implemented.

However, the company did not disclose much details about how to calculate and how to assess the above measurements. Therefore; I have summarized these measurements without recalculating them as the way of calculation is not disclosed. Below are the measurements in category wise:

a) *Supply chain*

The company has 22 different formulas to assess the achievements. These formulas are being sub-categorized into six difference sub-categories such as labor & human rights, health & safety, environment and management system.

b) Sustainable operations

There are 16 different formulas classified into 4 different sub-categories such as emissions, energy, water and waste.

c) Health and safety

Three different formulas such as injury and illness rate.

d) Communities

Five different formulas such as volunteer hours and contributions.

e) People

Seven formulas such as women team members and women in management.

If we compare the above measurements with the SDGs, we can say that the company is adopting good health & well-being (SDG 3), quality education (SDG 4), gender equality (SDG 5), clean water (SDG 6), clean energy (SDG 7), climate change (SDG 13), life on land (SDG 15).

Is the information real?

Before analyzing the accuracy of any report, we have first to understand what type of report we want to analyze. By asking ourselves this question, we will be able to know what criteria we should use to analyze. Report analysis is not something difficult, but it needs a high level of attention, going into details and the most important thing, being able to get information and link events with each other. However, there are three different types of reports. Let us start with the “self-produced reports”. We can define the self-produced reports as “documents that aim to ensure accountability that have the characteristics of providing a truthful account for an organization’s overall activities and should be prepared under a company’s own responsibility” (Rusconi & Contrafatto, 2013). If we analyze this definition, we can say that the CSR report issued by Dell for 2017-year end is a self-produced report.

The second type of report is “shadow reporting” which refers to “these coalition building accounts, which were not just used to reveal non-compliance, or make visible the ineffectiveness of regulatory regimes, but to create the potential for collective engagement and emancipatory changes”. Based on this, we may not only talk about critics, but we may also speak about some events made the organization change its policy, activities or practices towards the right path (Mercy, Ian, & Akira, 2018). In easier and simpler words, shadow report is not issued by the organization itself, it can be based on interviews with the employees, investigations, news or even scholars.

The third and the last reporting is the “silent report”, it refers to reports issued by the organization but verified by third party (Rob, 1997). The preparation of financial statements of a company is the responsibility of the management, but they should be verified and audited by third party, this is an example on “silent report”.

Based on the above types of reporting, I have analyzed the CSR report of Dell for 2017-year end. I used “self-produced report” which is the CSR report issued by Dell. The report is being prepared and issued by the company itself without having any verification, in other words; without having it verified by third party. I compared this “self-produced report” to the financial statements of the company which is “silent report” as it is being prepared by the company but verified by third party. As another step, I compared the report with news and other researches which are considered as “shadow reports” as these reports were prepared by third party without relying on any document issued by Dell itself.

In addition to the above, I have also assessed the language used by the company in the report and analyzed the level of it just to check if the report can be understood by any reader.

I started my analysis by collecting data about the same year end (2017) but I could not find much information fortunately! yes fortunately!! I will explain later why fortunately I could not find enough information. However, I decided to check what information I found and compare them with the CSR reports issued by Dell for the same period. In other words, if I find a case study on Dell in 2008, I will check the CSR report for 2008-year end. This step is just to ensure that whatever the company discloses is right, in other words; just to ensure the existence of the event. the next headlines are the events or the information I was able to collect. However, below are the events collected from “shadow report” and compared with “self-produced report”.

a) Dell as Ceres company

“CSRwire” which is a leading non-profit organization in sustainable activities consisted of corporations, agencies, universities and other firms such as the big four, had published in 2006 that Dell was approved as a Ceres company. For who does not know Ceres, Ceres is basically a non-profit advocacy organization specialized in sustainability. However, the approval came from the Board of Directors (thereafter “BoD”) of Ceres based on the following reasons (CSRwire, 2006):

- 1) Dell’s overall progress and commitment to social and environmental improvements,
- 2) Dell is the first in the industry to offer free recycling any brand of used computer or printer with the purchase of a new one from Dell.

The BoD of Ceres agreed and approved to include Dell in the community based on their meeting held in 2006 with showing all the evidences that agree on the 2 facts mentioned above.

I have compared the same event with the CSR report of 2006 which definitely was issued in 2007 to check if this event was included in the report and I noticed that the company had disclosed the same event in the report (Dell Technologies, 2007).

b) Three C’s strategy

According to the study done by Rao and Vanitha in 2016, “a study on green packaging – a case study approach with reference to Dell Inc.”, Dell is adopting the C’s strategy which aims to reduce the environmental footprint. This strategy is applied as follows (Priti & Vanitha, 2016):

- 1) Cube, which is the box itself,
- 2) Content, the material made of, and
- 3) Curb, the easiness of recycling

Cube, the size of the box is reduced. Reduction in packaging volume is achieved by reducing the size of boxes and cushions. Smaller boxes mean lower shipment cost and less usage of transportation space. Multipacks helps in cutting down the amount of cardboards needed.

Content and Curb, natural materials in packaging like bamboo and mushroom cushions, wheat straws, air carbon bags are used, and these materials are also easy for customers to recycle when they receive the packaged material. Straw is another sustainable packaging material used by Dell. They mix up with recycled paper fibers and created boxes for desktop and note pad products. This process uses less water and energy and is a part of green manufacturing.

By adopting ocean freight instead of air freight, the fuel needed per transaction is lesser. This has resulted in reduction of carbon emissions by 92%. However, by adopting the 3 C's strategy, approximately 66% of Dell shipments used packaging that is from 100% sustainable sources, by the end of 2015.

I have compared the above event with the CSR report issued by Dell in 2016 which related to 2015 year end, and I found that the company also disclosed the same event (Dell Technologies, 2017).

c) Businessfor2030

One of the SDGs framework subsidiaries published on its website that “Dell has launched EntrepreneursUNite in collaboration with the UN Foundation to ensure that SDG 8 is recognized as a priority by all Member States in the post-2015 development agenda...EntrepreneursUNite is a movement to help entrepreneurs scale globally to create the jobs the world needs and advance the greatest innovations of our time. EntrepreneursUNite has gathered over 21,000 signatures in support of this initiative” (businessfor2030, n.d.). This event was the only event I could not trace it to the report as the company did not disclose any event related to its economic performance in the CSR report.

d) 94% were sustainably sourced

Dell in its report for 2017 year end, disclosed that, “94% of Dell packaging materials by weight were sustainably sourced” (Dell Technologies, 2018), it is really huge percentage!

We all know that packaging step is part of cost of goods sold (thereafter “COGS”), therefore, I compared 2017's COGS with the 2016's COGS and I noticed that the COGS has increased by 21% in 2017 comparing to 2016, but is it a good indicator? Let us see. COGS alone do not make since, we should also have a look at the revenue for the same periods and then try to analyze, there is an increase by 27% in 2017 comparing to 2016 in revenue. We can see that both (revenue & COGS) have increased by different percentages. These increases led to increase in gross margin by 50%. This is what we should look at, the gross margin! the gross margin explains the profit on the products sold.

Let me explain it in easier words, when the revenue increases, it means that the company either sold more items or it increased the selling price on the products, when the COGS increases, it means that the company produced more items, and since more items produced, that means the revenue increased due to the increase in number of quantity sold. However, since the gross margin increased in 2017 comparing to 2016, that means the management was able to “manage” and “control” the cost, this can be done by implementing new technologies or new methods or recycling some of the raw materials which can be an indicator that what Dell disclosed about recycling 94% of the packaging material is right! However, for the numbers mentioned above, kindly refer to table 1.

Table 1. Income Statement (Form 10-K, 2019):

	<i>02-Feb-18</i>	<i>03-Feb-17</i>	<i>Change</i>	<i>Change</i>
	<i>USD Million</i>	<i>USD Million</i>	<i>USD Million</i>	<i>%</i>
<i>Revenue</i>	79,040	62,164	16,876	27%
<i>COGS</i>	(58,503)	(48,515)	(9,988)	21%
<i>Gross margin</i>	20,537	13,649	6,888	50%
<i>GM %</i>	26%	22%	-	4%
<i>Net loss</i>	(2,849)	(1,167)	(1,682)	144%

e) Pediatric rare cancers

The company disclosed in 2017’s sustainability report that it increased the funds to doctors who are specialized in treating the pediatric rare cancers, but the amount was not disclosed. I compared this information with the research and development expenses and I noticed that there is increase in research and development by USD 1,748 million in 2017 comparing to 2016 (Form 10-K, 2019) which can be an indicator that what the company disclosed about helping doctors in treating pediatric cancers is real.

So what?

From the above facts and analysis, I can say that what the company discloses (at least what I have covered) is real and exist. What gives me more assurance about this is that I could not find any “scandal” or “bad news” about the company, otherwise; I would have been able to get to know these news, especially that we all know the fact that the bad news “spread” rapidly especially when it comes to big companies or organizations and this is the reason why I said “fortunately” in the “***is the information real?***” section.

One more thing I have to mention is that the number of employees increased in 2017 comparing to 2016 by 35.56%, from 101,800 employees in 2016 to 138,000 employees in 2017 (marcotrends.net, 2019).

This is something is really appreciated and a good indicator that shows Dell is a company who has “friendly working environment”, otherwise; the number of employees would have been reduced or at least, the increase in the number of employees would not be that much high (35.56%).

Language used

This is something I should also mention, while I was reading the CSR report, I got lost in some parts, the language is not easy, and the consequence of the topics covered in the report some how does not make sense. If there is a reader who is not aware about this kind of reports, the reader would be lost. Let us have a look at the consequence according to the report.

The report begins with table of contents following to it; the letter from the management, but then? We go immediately to “achievements and challenges” which is really strange, the achievements and challenges should be disclosed after the “goals” of the company, otherwise; how the reader may understand or feel the difficulties the company faced to reach its goals or even how the reader can feel or appreciate the achievements done by the company before knowing its goals.

The second part was the goals of the company, as I mentioned above; I believe that the goals should be disclosed before the achievements and challenges.

In the third section of the report, the company is talking about the importance of products which we all are aware about it, but the question; why they disclose something almost everybody knows? even different brands customers appreciate Dell’s quality and products! The reputation which Dell has, is a good evidence!

Following to the importance of the products, Dell started to talk about how the products and its activities affect the environment, communities and people. Later on, Dell assigned a specific section to “how do they govern” after that they disclosed materiality according to the management supported with some facts and numbers (please refer to “*Measurements*” section).

In my opinion, the report should be simpler than this, the reader has to know at the beginning what is important to the management, therefore; I believe the consequence of the topics covered in the report should be as follows:

- 1) The materiality, as it gives a clear idea to the reader on what the company concerns about.
- 2) How do they govern, so the reader can have more comfort over what the company discloses in its materiality section, as it will show the reader how the company stops bad actions and how it makes the good ones based on the materiality.
- 3) Goals should be in third section, as definitely; after introducing what is material to the company and how the company governs to take care of these material things, the reader should have an idea about the goals of the company. This will give some how a wider idea about the company’s vision.

- 4) The challenges and the achievements of the company should be after the goals of the company. When the reader understands the vision of the company, the reader will be in a good position to evaluate the achievements and difficulties the company faced.
- 5) Now it will be the time of how the company's activities and products affected the environment, communities and people. The reader in this section would be able to assess the activities of the companies and evaluate them as well since the reader is part of the stakeholders.
- 6) The last thing should be the facts and numbers about the achievements with referring them to the goals disclosed in the third section in addition to clear explanation on how the company computes these numbers. This will give comfort to the reader and hence the trust increases.

GRI standards

GRI standards were defined in section "*Dell's CSR report*" section. The company as disclosed in its CSR report is adopting GRI standards, therefore; I decided to have a look at the standards issued by the framework itself and compare it to the CSR report issued by Dell for the year end of 2017.

GRI standards are divided into four different sections:

- 1) Section 101 refers to the "starting point of adopting GRI standards" divided into another two sections they are:
 - 1-A) Section 102 which refers to the general disclosures,
 - 1-B) Section 103 which refers to the management approach
- 2) Section 200s refers to economic performance of the company
- 3) Section 300s refers to the environmental impact of the company's activities and products
- 4) Section 400s refers to the social impact of the company's activities and products.

As I mentioned above, I decided to compare the GRI standards with the CSR report issued by the company and I noticed that the report is missing some information related to section 200s and section 400s. Below is the summary of the results:

- a) Economic performance (GRI 201), the company did not disclose any of its financial information in the CSR report
- b) Market presence (GRI 202), the company did not disclose the ratios of standard entry level wage by gender compared to the local minimum wage in addition to the proportion of senior management hired from the local community
- c) Indirect economic impact (GRI 203)
- d) Procurement practices (GRI 204)
- e) Anti-corruption (GRI 205), the only exception is that the company gives data privacy training to its employees
- f) Anti-competitive behavior (GRI 206)
- g) Local communities (GRI 413) which speaks about the operation with local community engagement and the operations with significant actual and potential negative impacts on local communities
- h) Public policy (GRI 415) which speaks about the political contribution

The company unfortunately did not disclose any information about the above standards, but when I noticed that it was generating losses in 2016 and 2017, I assumed that this is the reason. If a person reads the CSR report of Dell, the reader will notice and will get to know only the good things about the company and if the reader is not aware of the importance of the economic performance (can be checked from the financial statements), the reader would lose really important information. Anyway, let us don't go far! The CSR report is being issued to communicate the social achievements or the social activities of the company to the stakeholders, and as I mentioned in "*Dell's CSR report*" section, the shareholders are part of the stakeholders and in this case, whatever important information concerned by the shareholders, should be available in the report itself especially if the reader want to get high-level analysis about the economic performance without referring to any other report.

Conclusion

As a conclusion, the CSR report of Dell is enough for the stakeholders in general, and I believe based on the analysis I did, that the information disclosed in the report are real and they really exist. Unfortunately, I could not make a deeper analysis due to the confidentiality of the information as I relied only on the information disclosed on internet, articles, case studies and books. However, I noticed that the company in compliance also with the SDGs goals which were supported by public news and high-level analysis done based on the financial statements and based on other resources.

I noticed as well that the language used in the report and the consequence of the topics, make the reader lose the concentration. The topics are not linked to each other in a proper way and if the reader is not aware of the importance or the purpose of the CSR report, the reader would not understand the content of the report itself.

The last thing I noticed is that the report is missing some important standards since it is adopting GRI standards. These standards make the report to lose an important stakeholder who is the shareholder. The shareholder if concerned about the economic performance, definitely not this report is the one he/she needs. In addition to this, some other standards are missed such as social standards as well.

However, Dell is a big company at the end, and the management are aware of what they do, therefore; I believe, the reason of not including the economic performance is to attract investors and the reason for not writing in a simple language is that the management wants investors who are aware about the importance of every single action or activity being done by the company, not only the operational activities, but also the reporting activities.

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